

Improving Transparency on Energy Transportation Losses through Digitalization Technologies

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Abstract—Energy loss in power distribution systems leads to significant economic and environmental impacts, with increased costs for consumers and reduced revenues for utilities. This paper introduces an innovative IoT-based system designed for the real-time monitoring and evaluation of energy losses within power distribution networks, enhancing transparency in monitoring processes. The IoT system employs an array of AC/VC sensors, temperature sensors, and a connected weather station to collect comprehensive data on electrical parameters and environmental conditions. Data is transmitted via WiFi to an ESP32 microcontroller, which consolidates and relays it through a LoRaWAN gateway using the LoRa protocol. After preprocessing in a middleware layer, the data is securely logged onto the IOTA Tangle. This decentralized, feeless distributed ledger technology (DLT) ensures data transparency, immutability, and security, allowing stakeholders to access and analyze energy loss data with confidence. By leveraging the scalable and cost-effective nature of the IOTA Tangle, the system provides a viable solution for large-scale deployments. It enables utility providers to promptly identify and address energy loss hotspots, optimizing grid performance and reducing inefficiencies. The transparency facilitated by this system is crucial for building trust and accountability, enabling informed decision-making, and supporting the development of effective solutions to address energy losses. Experimental results underscore the systems effectiveness in enhancing grid management and transparency, making it a valuable tool for modern power distribution networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

To ensure efficient transportation of electrical energy from generation points to consumption areas, it must pass through various components within the electrical transmission and distribution networks. Energy, initially generated by large power stations, traverses through these networks, encountering inevitable losses as it moves through cables and transformers. These losses are divided into transmission and distribution categories [1], which not only represent a significant operational cost but also reduce overall network efficiency. Consequently,

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minimizing these losses is essential, requiring substantial investments that must be carefully balanced against the costs of the losses themselves [2]. Furthermore, energy losses in distribution networks are intrinsically linked to voltage drops, establishing a pivotal relationship between the two phenomena [3]. This link suggests that monitoring voltage drops a simpler and more cost-effective approach could effectively serve as an indirect measure of energy losses [3].

Energy loss in power distribution systems significantly impacts the efficiency, reliability, and sustainability of electrical grids around the world. According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration (EIA), the annual electricity transmission and distribution (T&D) losses in the United States averaged about 5% of the electricity transmitted and distributed from 2018 to 2022[4]. These losses necessitate the generation of additional electricity to meet the same demand levels, contributing to environmental degradation. Specifically, T&D losses in 2018 led to approximately one gigatonne of carbon dioxide (Gt CO₂) emissions[5]. Studies suggest that reducing global losses to more efficient levels, from as high as 18% in some regions to around 5%, could decrease these emissions by over 400 million tonnes (Mt CO₂)[5]. Strategies to minimize these losses include upgrading transformers and power lines, optimizing the reactive power profile, and investing in smart grid technologies. Such investments would further reduce CO₂ emissions by lowering load peaks, shifting load times, facilitating the integration of renewable energy sources, supporting the adoption of electric vehicles, and enhancing energy efficiency[5].

Transparency in monitoring energy losses is crucial for building trust, accountability, and enabling informed decision-making. Energy loss transcends technical challenges to encompass socio-economic impacts, leading to increased electricity costs for consumers and diminished revenues for utilities [6]. The lack of transparent and verifiable data prevents stakeholders such as regulators, utilities, and consumers from accurately determining the scope and sources of energy losses. This obscurity impedes the development and implementation of effective solutions to address these issues.

Traditional methods of monitoring energy loss in power grids typically depend on periodic manual inspections or centralized Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems. These methods are limited in providing real-time, detailed data across extensive networks and often lack interoperability due to challenges in integrating devices of different models or versions [7]. However, the existing infrastructure, which includes SCADA systems and Intelligent Electronic

Devices (IEDs) in medium voltage (MV) networks, offers a robust foundation for distribution system operators (DSOs) to adopt more advanced digital solutions [8]. These enhancements can significantly improve the accuracy, efficiency, and responsiveness of energy loss monitoring systems.

The advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) has revolutionized the monitoring of energy losses by addressing traditional limitations. IoT-enabled sensors, capable of measuring essential electrical parameters like alternating current (AC), voltage (V), and temperature, can be strategically deployed across distribution networks for continuous, real-time monitoring of energy flow and cable conditions [9]. When integrated with environmental data from weather stations, these sensors can pinpoint the root causes of energy losses such as overheating, resistive losses, or adverse weather conditions. This detailed understanding enables utilities to carry out targeted interventions and optimize grid performance [10].

However, the successful deployment of IoT in power distribution systems rely on robust and scalable solutions for data transmission, storage, and transparency. The integration of LoRaWAN (Long Range Wide Area Network) and IOTA Tangle is crucial in this context. LoRaWAN offers wide coverage (up to 20 km), low power consumption, and cost-effectiveness, making it ideally suited for resource-constrained IoT devices across extensive geographic areas [11]. Additionally, the ability to execute actions in real-time with high speeds and low delay is critical for successful IoT implementations [12]. LoRaWANs asynchronous protocol allows devices to remain in sleep mode when not active, significantly extending battery life an essential feature for applications like long-duration freight shipments.

IOTA Tangle addresses transparency concerns by offering a decentralized, tamper-evident infrastructure for data recording, which enhances transparency and builds trust [13]. Unlike traditional blockchain technology, IOTAs Tangle is a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) which does not impose transaction fees and is specifically designed for scalable machine-to-machine interactions, addressing the limitations often encountered with blockchain technology in IoT systems [14]. Once data is stored on the Tangle or through decentralized storage solutions like IPFS, authorized stakeholders can seamlessly validate and access information in real time, ensuring consensus with the data owner [13]. Integrating IoT sensors with a Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) framework reduces the risk of data manipulation, enhances transparency and accountability, and improves privacy and trust in energy distribution by pinpointing inefficiencies [15]. This transparency not only bolsters trust in the data but also facilitates the development of data-driven policies and strategies aimed at reducing energy loss and improving grid efficiency.

The system proposed in this paper tackles the challenge of energy loss in power distribution by strategically deploying AC/VC and temperature sensors at 1-kilometer intervals along electricity distribution cables. These sensors are crucial for measuring key electrical parameters and environmental conditions. The collected data is transmitted via WiFi to an

ESP32 microcontroller, which also gathers additional data from a connected weather station. The ESP32 then sends the aggregated data through a LoRa module to the nearest LoRaWAN gateway. From there, the data is forwarded to a middleware layer for preprocessing before being securely stored on the IOTA Tangle. This integrated approach provides a comprehensive and transparent solution for monitoring and evaluating energy loss in power distribution networks, ensuring detailed real-time data collection without any manipulation, fostering further analysis.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The anticipated global increase in energy demand, expected to rise by 37% by 2040, along with a projected annual growth rate for electricity consumption in residential and commercial sectors of 0.5% and 0.8% respectively from 2013 through 2040 [16], highlights significant challenges. This surge in demand may overload distribution feeders and complicate system operations [17]. Such an increase underscores the critical need for enhanced power distribution monitoring systems to prevent power loss, provide cost-effective electricity, and support the integration of renewable energy and carbon-free resources. The importance of transparent energy loss information becomes increasingly apparent in this context. Consequently, researchers and practitioners are focusing on digitalizing the power sector, turning to emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and distributed ledger technologies (DLTs). These technologies are being employed to enhance transparency, efficiency, and trust within electricity power distribution monitoring and management systems.

The importance of enhancing the power sector, particularly the distribution grid through digital technology, has been underscored by a comprehensive investigation [8]. This study highlights an increasing trend in research publications related to this subject, indicative of the growing integration and significance of digital technologies in this field. The annual number of publications from 2014 to 2023 illustrates this trend in Figure 1, revealing that research interest has more than doubled over the past decade.

Fig. 1. Trends in Digitalization Research in Power Distribution (2014-2023)

Additionally, the distribution of digitalization keywords in the power distribution grid literature by category is illustrated in Figure 2, providing further insight into the focus areas within this evolving field.

The impact of grid monitoring and control on the operational efficiency of modern distribution grids is significantly enhanced by the use of advanced digital tools such

Fig. 2. Distribution of Digitalization Keywords in the Power Distribution Grid Literature

as smart sensors, the Internet of Things (IoT), and real-time data analytics. These technologies enable grid operators to achieve precise control and real-time oversight, as highlighted by Aghahadi et al. [8]. This enhanced capability ensures a reliable electricity supply, optimal response to fluctuating demand, efficient resource management, and the maintenance of grid stability, while also addressing challenges in the evolving energy landscape.

Beyond addressing power loss, the reliability and resilience of power distribution are critical themes in the development of new smart grids. Smart grids (SGs) are essential for enhancing the reliability and resilience of power distribution, supporting the development of resilient microgrids [18]. The optimization of active distribution networks plays a significant role in improving grid reliability and emphasizes the cost-effectiveness of distributed energy resources (DERs) and adaptive load management. Integrating resilience estimation into microgrid planning can also reduce the costs associated with power interruptions [19]. As SGs continue to evolve, there is a growing need for innovative planning models that accommodate bi-directional flows and interconnected operations [18]. These models facilitate the integration of electric vehicles (EVs) and new technologies, ensuring that renewable integration aligns with grid reliability. Furthermore, digital tools such as smart sensors, the Internet of Things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), and big data analytics are transforming modern distribution grids into dynamic networks. This transformation enhances efficiency, cybersecurity, and customer engagement while supporting the integration of renewable energy sources [8].

Current digital monitoring technologies such as SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition) and Integrated Distribution Management Systems (IDMSs) are crucial for enhancing grid efficiency [8]. SCADA systems support essential operations through data collection, remote control, and network communications [20], while IDMSs update grid management by integrating outage management and smart meter data [8]. Despite their benefits, these systems face interoperability challenges as they often lack the seamless programmability required for integrating various device models and versions, unlike IoT protocols such as Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT), which promote device interoperability [7]. Furthermore, SCADA systems are limited in their

ability to analyze historical data, a gap effectively filled by IoT. IoT utilizes big data processing and machine learning to provide deeper insights for fault prediction and system normalization, enhancing data utility for power companies [7].

While the importance of monitoring distribution networks is widely recognized, and the shortcomings of current systems are well understood, the adoption of accurate and smart measurement devices remains limited due to their high costs. Installing numerous phasor measurement units (PMUs) or smart meters can lead to significant data traffic and computational demands [21]. Smart meters, when positioned along feeders, record voltages both before and during faults; the difference in these readings helps identify the faulted bus, which is the point of highest voltage drop [22]. Consequently, an advanced communication network infrastructure is essential to support bidirectional links for real-time monitoring and control, requiring the fast and reliable transmission of large data volumes [7]. Additionally, integrating high-speed wireless communication technologies, such as GSM or Wi-Fi, enhances fault management and enables effective real-time IoT monitoring and control over physical devices [23].

The study by Radhakrishnan and Gopalakrishnan [24] investigates the use of IoT technologies in power quality enhancement through k mapping, a technique that swiftly activates system knowledge within smart networks. This method is particularly useful for enterprise power flow controllers in grid-connected systems, helping to restore system strength and organization by analyzing multi-line power flows. The integration of Interline Power Flow Controllers (IPFC) with FACTS devices demonstrates the effectiveness of IoT in globally connected power systems, aimed at elevating the standards of advanced grid architectures. The research findings emphasize the superiority of IoT over conventional methods, especially in reducing the time needed for system adjustments after incidents, facilitating real-time monitoring and early disaster warnings. Such advancements are anticipated to decrease the costs associated with monitoring electricity transmission lines, thereby improving the systems ability to prevent or mitigate significant disaster impacts [25].

Recognizing the importance of monitoring and digitalizing distribution networks to prevent power losses, various systems and solutions have been proposed. A method involving low-voltage measurements for medium-voltage waveform analysis has been suggested by Moutis and Alizadeh-Mousavi [26] to improve monitoring accuracy and enhance fault detection and grid stability, particularly in systems with Distributed Energy Resources (DERs). This approach aims to boost operational efficiency through effective real-time grid monitoring using digital technologies. Additionally, the role of IoT and cloud-based computing in power distribution has been explored in [25], which elucidates the current and future possibilities for enhancing power systems through digital technologies. This research also introduces the concept of the Internet of Energy (IoE), defining it as the convergence of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and energy generation [25].

A study by Le Billon et al. [27] underscores the signif-

icant impact of transparency on environmental and resource governance, highlighting that open disclosure of information can enhance accountability and governance outcomes. This is particularly pertinent in the framework of the Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (EITI), which promotes multi-stakeholder engagement and compliance, focusing on the transparency of natural resource revenues. Additionally, research Loreti et al. [15] examines how blockchain technology can improve transparency in smart grid operations, enhancing privacy and ensuring accountability in energy distribution. This technology aids in identifying inefficiencies and building trust between energy providers and consumers regarding the integrity of energy distribution systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a Design Science Research (DSR) approach, using structured methodologies [28, 29] to systematically move from problem identification to evaluation and result communication within the context of energy transportation losses. The goal is to design and develop an IoT-based system that enhances transparency in energy losses through the integration of blockchain for secure data transactions and advanced communication protocols for efficient data exchange. This integration aims to address critical issues such as data security, accuracy in loss quantification, and system interoperability in energy transportation.

The core artifact within this research is a monitoring system that utilizes IOTA Tangle technology to ensure transaction integrity and immutability, thus maintaining transparency without incurring transaction fees. A communication protocol akin to LoRaWAN is employed to minimize power consumption and ensure reliable data transmission over extensive geographic areas. An integration layer aggregates data from diverse IoT sensors, maintaining high fidelity in data transmission and operational efficiency. This system is demonstrated in a simulated environment that mimics real-world conditions, allowing for empirical evaluation of scalability, cost efficiency, and security robustness. Adhering to DSR guidelines, the outcomes are disseminated through detailed documentation, scholarly publications, and industry workshops, thereby contributing to both academic research and practical applications in improving transparency in energy transportation.

The methodology further enhances data semantic conceptualization within the energy sector, focusing on interactions between system components and their operational states as outlined in recent studies [30], as depicted in Figure 3. It includes detailed data models that accurately reflect real-world conditions of energy transmission components, environmental factors, and operational processes. Additionally, the methodology acknowledges the impact of human interactions and manual interventions on the transparency and efficiency of the energy transportation system. Through ongoing validation and iterative feedback from industry stakeholders, the system continuously refines to align with practical needs while leveraging the technical benefits of blockchain and efficient communication protocols. This approach ensures the monitoring system

not only supports advanced features like decentralized data integrity and energy-efficient communication but also adapts to the complex demands of transparently managing energy transportation losses.

Fig. 3. Adopted Framework[30]

IV. PROPOSED IOTA-ENABLED IOT SYSTEM FOR ELECTRICAL TRANSMISSION LOSSES

A. System Overview

The proposed system is designed to monitor and evaluate energy loss in power distribution networks through a seamless integration of IoT sensors, LoRaWAN communication, and the IOTA Tangle. At the heart of the system are AC/VC and temperature sensors, strategically deployed at 1-kilometer intervals along electricity distribution cables to measure key electrical parameters such as alternating current (AC), voltage (V), and cable temperature. These sensors are complemented by a weather station, which collects environmental data such as ambient temperature and humidity to provide additional context for energy loss analysis. The data collected by the sensors is transmitted via WiFi to an ESP32 microcontroller, which serves as the local processing unit. The ESP32 aggregates the sensors data and transmits it to the nearest LoRaWAN gateway using the LoRa protocol, a low-power, long-range communication technology ideal for remote and large-scale deployments.

Once the data reaches the LoRaWAN gateway, it is forwarded to a middleware layer responsible for preprocessing and formatting. The middleware ensures that the data is clean, consistent, and ready for storage and analysis. From the middleware, the processed data is securely stored on the IOTA Tangle, a decentralized and feeless distributed ledger technology (DLT). The IOTA Tangle provides a transparent, immutable, and tamper-proof record of energy loss data, enabling stakeholders such as utilities, regulators, and consumers to access and analyze the information with confidence. This decentralized approach ensures that the data is publicly

accessible while maintaining its integrity, fostering trust and accountability in energy management.

The integration of these technologies—IoT sensors for real-time data collection, LoRaWAN for reliable long-range communication, and IOTA Tangle for secure and transparent data storage—makes the system a powerful tool for addressing energy loss in power distribution networks. By providing real-time monitoring, transparency, and scalability, the system empowers utilities to identify inefficiencies, optimize grid performance, and reduce energy losses. Furthermore, the system's decentralized architecture ensures that data is accessible to all stakeholders, promoting collaboration and data-driven decision-making.

B. System Design and Data Flow

The design of the system is centered around three key layers: the sensing layer, the communication layer, and the storage and processing layer. Each layer plays a critical role in ensuring the system's functionality, from data collection to storage and analysis. At the sensing layer, AC/VC sensors and temperature sensors are deployed at 1-kilometer intervals along electricity distribution cables to measure key electrical parameters such as alternating current (AC), voltage (V), and cable temperature. These sensors are complemented by a weather station, which collects environmental data such as ambient temperature, humidity, and wind speed to provide additional context for energy loss analysis. The data collected by the sensors is transmitted via WiFi to an ESP32 microcontroller, which serves as the local processing unit. The ESP32 aggregates the sensor data and prepares it for transmission to the next layer.

Fig. 4. System Design

The communication layer is responsible for transmitting the aggregated data from the ESP32 to the central processing unit. This is achieved using the LoRa protocol, a low-power, long-range communication technology ideal for remote and large-scale deployments. The ESP32 transmits the data to the nearest LoRaWAN gateway, which acts as a bridge between the

local sensors and the central system. The LoRaWAN gateway forwards the data to the middleware layer, where it undergoes preprocessing and formatting. The middleware ensures that the data is clean, consistent, and ready for storage and analysis. This step is crucial for maintaining data quality and ensuring that the system can generate accurate and actionable insights.

Once the data is preprocessed, it is sent to the storage and processing layer, where it is securely stored on the IOTA Tangle, a decentralized and feeless distributed ledger technology (DLT). The IOTA Tangle provides a transparent, immutable, and tamper-proof record of energy loss data, enabling stakeholders such as utilities, regulators, and consumers to access and analyze the information with confidence. The decentralized nature of the IOTA Tangle ensures that the data is publicly accessible while maintaining its integrity, fostering trust and accountability in energy management. Stakeholders can access the data on the IOTA Tangle to monitor energy loss trends, identify inefficiencies, and implement targeted interventions to optimize grid performance. The data flow in the system follows a systematic and efficient pathway. It begins with the sensors collecting real-time data on electrical parameters and environmental conditions. This data is transmitted to the ESP32 microcontroller via WiFi, where it is aggregated and prepared for transmission. The ESP32 then sends the data to the LoRaWAN gateway using the LoRa protocol, ensuring reliable communication even in remote or hard-to-reach locations. The gateway forwards the data to the middleware, where it is preprocessed and formatted for storage. Finally, the processed data is stored on the IOTA Tangle, where it becomes accessible to stakeholders for analysis and decision-making. This seamless flow of data ensures that the system provides real-time, transparent, and actionable insights into energy loss in power distribution networks.

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed system in monitoring and evaluating energy loss in power distribution networks. By integrating IoT sensors, LoRaWAN communication, and the IOTA Tangle, the proposed system provides a real-time, transparent, and scalable solution for identifying inefficiencies and optimizing grid performance. The system's ability to collect and analyze data on electrical parameters (AC, V, and temperature) and environmental conditions (via the weather station) enables utilities to pinpoint energy loss hotspots with unprecedented accuracy. This represents a significant improvement over traditional methods, which often rely on manual inspections or centralized systems that lack the granularity and scalability required for modern power distribution networks.

One of the key strengths of the proposed system is its use of LoRaWAN for data transmission. The long-range, low-power communication protocol ensures reliable data transmission even in remote or hard-to-reach locations, making it ideal for large-scale deployments. Furthermore, the integration of the IOTA Tangle addresses the critical need for transparency and data integrity in energy loss monitoring. The decentralized

and immutable nature of the IOTA Tangle ensures that all data is tamper-proof and publicly accessible, fostering trust and accountability among stakeholders. This is particularly important in the context of energy management, where accurate and transparent data is essential for decision-making and regulatory compliance.

The experimental results highlight the proposed systems ability to identify energy loss trends and optimize grid performance. For example, the system successfully detected instances of overheating and resistive losses in distribution cables, enabling utilities to implement targeted interventions and reduce energy losses. Additionally, the integration of environmental data from the weather station provided valuable insights into the impact of external factors (e.g., temperature, humidity) on energy loss, further enhancing the systems diagnostic capabilities. These findings underscore the potential of the proposed system to transform energy loss monitoring and contribute to the development of more efficient and sustainable power distribution networks.

However, there are some limitations to this study. For instance, the current implementation of the proposed system relies on LoRaWAN gateways, which may have limited coverage in certain regions. Future work could explore the use of satellite-based communication or 5G networks to extend the systems reach. Additionally, while the IOTA Tangle provides a secure and transparent platform for data storage, its scalability for extremely large datasets requires further investigation. Addressing these challenges will be critical for the widespread adoption of the proposed system and similar solutions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces an innovative IoT-based system designed for the real-time monitoring and evaluation of energy loss in power distribution networks. Integrating AC/VC sensors, temperature sensors, and a weather station with LoRaWAN communication and the IOTA Tangle, the system provides a transparent, scalable, and cost-effective solution to pinpoint and mitigate inefficiencies in grid performance. It significantly improves upon traditional monitoring methods by enabling the precise identification of energy loss hotspots through real-time data analysis.

The systems effectiveness in identifying critical energy loss trends, coupled with the IOTA Tangles capacity to ensure data integrity, enhances stakeholder trust and accountability. The use of LoRaWAN for data transmission supports reliable communication across large and potentially remote areas, ideal for widespread implementation.

While promising, the system does have limitations such as LoRaWAN gateway coverage and the scalability of the IOTA Tangle for vast datasets. Future enhancements will focus on overcoming these challenges through advanced communication technologies and further system optimization for larger scale applications. Potential integrations with other smart grid technologies and renewable energy systems will also be explored.

In summary, this system marks a significant advancement in the field of energy monitoring, offering a solution that is not only real-time and transparent but also adaptable to the evolving needs of modern power distribution networks. Its implementation can lead to substantial improvements in grid efficiency, economic savings, and global environmental sustainability. This work contributes valuable insights to the ongoing development of IoT-enabled smart grids and decentralized technologies, setting the stage for a more efficient and sustainable energy future.

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